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Robotics Development Hierarchy in Uzbekistan: Institutions, Strategy, and Emerging Ecosystem

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Abstract. This paper explores the structured development of robotics in Uzbekistan, examining national strategies, academic programs, innovation hubs, and industry involvement. It highlights the growing ecosystem through governmental initiatives, international collaborations, and educational reforms. The study provides a comprehensive view of how Uzbekistan is shaping its robotics landscape across policy, training, and application domains.

Keywords: Robotics, automation, education, innovation, policy, startups

Иерархия развития робототехники в Узбекистане: институты, стратегия и формирующаяся экосистема

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Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается структурированное развитие робототехники в Узбекистане, изучаются национальные стратегии, академические программы, инновационные центры и участие промышленности. В ней подчеркивается растущая экосистема посредством правительственных инициатив, международного сотрудничества и образовательных реформ. Исследование дает всестороннее представление о том, как Узбекистан формирует свой ландшафт робототехники в политике, обучении и областях применения.

Ключевые слова: робототехника, автоматизация, образование, инновации, политика, стартапы

O'zbekistonda robototexnikani rivojlantirish ierarxiyasi: institutlar, strategiya va rivojlanayotgan ekotizim.

A'zamjon Yaxyozoda, Rasulov Muhammadaziz

Farg'ona davlat texnika universiteti

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda robototexnikaning tizimli rivojlanishi, milliy strategiyalar, o'quv dasturlari, innovatsion markazlar va sanoat ishtiroki ko'rib chiqiladi. Unda hukumat tashabbuslari, xalqaro hamkorlik va ta'lim sohasidagi islohotlar orqali o'sib borayotgan ekotizimga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqot O'zbekiston o'zining robototexnika landshaftini siyosat, ta'lim va qo'llash sohalarida qanday shakllantirayotgani haqida har tomonlama tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: robototexnika, avtomatlashtirish, ta'lim, innovatsiyalar, siyosat, startaplar

Introduction

In the past decade, Uzbekistan has demonstrated significant ambition in advancing its technological capabilities, particularly in robotics and automation. Guided by strategic national policies and supported by international partnerships, the country is building an integrated system of education, research, and industry focused on robotics. This paper investigates the hierarchical development of this field, tracing contributions from government, academia, and private sectors. The objective is to map the ecosystem and understand the drivers and limitations in developing a sustainable robotics landscape.

Government Strategy and Policy Framework

Uzbekistan's strategic commitment to digital transformation is captured in national programs like *"Digital Uzbekistan – 2030"* and the *AI Development Strategy until 2030*. These frameworks aim to integrate robotics and automation across sectors by: - Establishing a dedicated **Department for AI Development** under the Ministry of Digital Technologies - Launching the **Digital Technologies Development Fund**, which allocates millions of dollars to tech startups and research - Supporting human capital development through the **"One Million Uzbek Coders"** initiative, a large-scale public coding education project

These policies not only support robotics-specific innovation but also form part of a broader drive to digitalize the economy and improve educational access to 21st-century skills.

Academic and Training Institutions

Uzbekistan's universities play a vital role in robotics development. Several have established new degree programs in robotics, mechatronics, and AI. Key institutions include:

Andijan Machine-Building Institute (AndMI): A leading regional technical university and a key member of the EU-funded *MechaUz* project, which modernized mechatronics programs.

Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent (TTPU): Developed in cooperation with Italy's Politecnico di Torino, focusing on mechatronics and automotive robotics.

Tashkent State Technical University (TSTU): Hosts automation labs and participates in research collaboration networks.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies (TUIT): Spearheads doctoral programs in AI and intelligent systems.

The MechaUz project deserves special mention. It developed 12 new mechatronics courses and set up **Industry 4.0 laboratories** in five Uzbek universities, training faculty abroad and aligning local curricula with EU standards.

Research Centers and Innovation Hubs

Government-led and university-based R&D centers are crucial nodes in Uzbekistan's robotics ecosystem:

The **Ministry of Innovative Development** headquarters houses advanced robotics labs, AI software development spaces, and an aerospace prototyping zone.

The **U-ENTER Innovation Center** provides maker labs, Arduino kits, and 3D printers for rapid prototyping.

The **Center for Youth Initiatives (CFYI)** promotes hands-on STEAM education and runs a dedicated robotics laboratory.

These hubs not only advance research but also provide platforms for student experimentation and public engagement.

Private Sector and Startup Ecosystem

Although still in early stages, Uzbekistan's private sector shows growing interest in robotics:

NUWA Robotics (Taiwan) signed an agreement to establish a local presence in collaboration with **IT Park Uzbekistan**.

TechnoRobotics Ltd., an Israeli-Uzbek-German startup, partners with TTPU to develop collaborative robotic arms (cobots).

Local manufacturers like **UzAuto Motors** are gradually integrating robotic automation in their production lines.

Investment and support come from entities like the **Digital Technologies Development Fund**, **KOICA** (Korea), and EU programs like **Erasmus+**.

Education Pipeline and Talent Development

Robotics education begins at extracurricular levels and progresses into formal university training:

Programs like *One Million Uzbek Coders* and **STEAM** camps teach programming to students as young as 13.

Private academies and regional centers run workshops using platforms like **Arduino** and **Lego Mindstorms**.

High-performing students attend specialized tech lyceums, progressing to university degrees in automation, robotics, or AI.

Gifted youth are often identified through competitions or **STEM Olympiads**, ensuring a steady flow of talent into higher education.

Competitions and Public Engagement

Public robotics competitions are a cornerstone of Uzbekistan's outreach efforts:

Robot-uz Championship: Held annually with categories like robo-football and robo-maze. In 2024, over 560 students participated.

FIRST Global Challenge: Uzbekistan sends finalists to compete internationally, gaining exposure and experience.

University Hackathons and Demo Days: Organized by IT Park, U-ENTER, and institutions like TUIT, often featuring IoT and automation themes.

These events not only inspire young learners but also promote innovation visibility and national pride.

Funding and International Collaboration

Uzbekistan's robotics growth is supported by diverse funding and partnerships:

National budgets through the **Digital Technologies Development Fund**

International grants via **Erasmus+ (EU)** and **KOICA (South Korea)**

Academic exchanges and tech alliances with Israel, Germany, Italy, UAE, and South Korea

These collaborations bring not only funding but also technical know-how, helping local institutions upgrade their infrastructure and academic standards.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan is creating a layered ecosystem for robotics development—from top-level policy frameworks and ministerial investments to university programs, local startups, and public competitions. The country is transitioning from consumer to

contributor in the robotics and automation sectors. Key challenges include maintaining momentum, integrating robotics more deeply into school curricula, and fostering sustained industry-academic collaboration. However, the groundwork laid over the past five years positions Uzbekistan as a promising emerging player in the global robotics landscape.

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